

THE ROLE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ECONOMY

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Abstract: The article examines the reasons for the transition to the digital economy, its features, main components and development prospects. Currently, in many developed countries, digitalization has been introduced in all sectors of life, and this, therefore, will lead to an increase in productivity and, consequently, competitiveness.

Keywords: ICT, digital economy, Internet economy, digitalization. **Annotatsiya:** Maqolada raqamli iqtisodiyotga o'tish sabablari, xususiyatlari, asosiy tarkibiy qismlari va rivojlanish istiqbollari ko'rib chiqilgan. Hozirgi kunda ko'plab rivojlangan mamlakatlar raqamlashtirishni hayotning barcha sohalariga tadbiq etmoqdalar va shuning uchun bu samaradorlikning oshishiga, natijada raqobatbardoshlikka olib keladi.

Kalit so'zlar: AKT, raqamli iqtisodiyot, Internet-iqtisod, raqamlashtirish.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается причины перехода к цифровой экономике, ее особенности, основные компоненты и перспективы развития. В настоящее время во многих развитых странах внедрили цифровизацию во все отрасли жизнедеятельности, а это, следовательно, приведет к увеличению производительности, а следовательно, и конкурентоспособности.

Ключевые слова: ИКТ, цифровая экономика, Интернет-экономика, цифровизация.

The main trend in the global economic development of the late XX – early XXI century is the transition from the industrial and post-industrial economy to the so-called digital economy, that is, an economy based on digital technologies or the use of information and communication technologies (hereinafter ICT). The

development of the Internet and mobile communications are the "basic technologies of the digital economy".

The digital economy is not some new economy, but the next stage in the development of the existing one, and the digitalization of the entire economy is considered at the state level as a strategic direction for the development of society, ensuring economic growth and competitiveness.

In this regard, the developed countries of the world pay close attention to the harmonious development of the system-forming elements of the digital economy, the information society and the knowledge economy. The need to transition to an information economy has also developed in Uzbekistan, which, in particular, was reflected in the formation of a special strategy "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" (approved by Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. UP – 6079, dated October 5, 2020).

After the financial crisis of 2007-2008, which began in the United States and then spread to Europe and Asia, the world economy entered a new stage [1]. Traditional economic development was slowing down, while the digital economy, represented by new generation technologies such as mobile Internet, cloud computing, big data analytics and artificial intelligence (AI), began to develop actively [2]. At a time when international digitalization and informatization are entering an era of more complete penetration into all spheres of human activity, based on innovation and information, the digital economy has really become a new engine of economic growth. [3]

Thus, the digital economy includes a variety of economic activities, where the use of digital information and knowledge plays the role of a key factor of production and modern information networks become an important area of activity, and the effective use of ICT acts as an effective driving force for improving efficiency and optimizing the structure of the economy. [4]

In 1985, when the first domain was registered and the world economy began to move to the "network". Since that time, the Internet economy has begun to

expand its scale of services, customer base, geographical coverage, and transformed into a new type of business activity. In the conditions of mass use of information networks, the network economy has also appeared – it is a combination of the traditional economy with the use of information resources of networks and technologies. At the same time, the concept of electronic economy appeared, implying trade on the Internet, that is, the main production functions are concentrated in e-commerce.

Currently, the world is entering the era of the post-industrial digital economy, which is radically changing the situation:

- Information becomes the main resource, and this source does not run out of use;
- Retail space on the Internet is not limited;
- A company doesn't need to be big to compete successfully;
- The same physical resource can be used an infinite number of times to provide various services;
- The scale of operational activity is limited only by the size of the Internet;
- The client becomes a "deity". [5]

The digital economy includes the following key components:

- technological infrastructure (hardware, software and communication networks);
- digital processes (processes that ensure successful business);
- e-commerce (sale of goods via the Internet);

It should be noted that in 2019, the total amount of electronic transactions in Uzbekistan amounted to \$ 344.3 million, and the annual growth of the share of e-commerce in the country's GDP is estimated at 30%. Namely, the volume of trade via the Internet in 2019 amounted to 275.3 billion soums (the growth rate is 6.7 times), which is 0.11 percent of the total trade volume of the republic. These figures show that the phenomenon of e-commerce has very bright prospects [6], [7], [8].

Digital transformations are changing the face and structure of the economy, breaking the usual business models, leading to the expansion of markets and opportunities, becoming the most important engine of global economic growth. Today, 75% of professions require basic digital skills, and about 44% of companies in the world have a digital development strategy. The very word "digitalization" implies the existence of a single information space for the continuous exchange of data between various fields of activity and structural units [9], [10], [11].

Currently, many developed countries have implemented digitalization in all sectors of life. In turn, the digitalization of the country's economy will lead to an increase in productivity and, consequently, competitiveness.

It should be noted that the formation of the digital economy has destroyed old industries and created completely new ones. The digital revolution or the benefits of this leap will become even more tangible if the spread of ICT is stimulated and directed by the state, and then coverage will be 100 percent.

REFERENCES:

1. Shadieva, G. M., & o'g'li Isoqulov, Z. S. (2022). WAYS TO REDUCE POVERTY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 957-962.
2. Mardievna, S. G., & Oblokulovich, K. S. (2021). Methodology for determining the role of family business in the economy. *European Business and Management*, 7(6), 199.
3. Shadieva, G. M., & Akbarovna, K. S. (2023). PROVIDING EMPLOYMENT BY IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF FAMILY BUSINESSES. *Journal of new century innovations*, 20(3), 25-31.
4. Shadieva, G., Azamatovna, T. D., & Abdukhalilovich, S. B. (2022). The role of retail trade in increasing the standard of living of the population. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE &*

INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11, 64-67.

5. Shadiyeva, G. (2022). The Role of Family Business in the Development of the Service Industry. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 5(9), 213-218.
6. Shadiyeva, G. (2022). The Role of Family Business in the Development of the Service Industry. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 5(9), 213-218.
7. Shadiyeva, G. M., & Akbarovna, K. S. (2023). THE CONCEPT OF "FAMILY ECONOMY", ITS DEVELOPMENT. *Journal of new century innovations*, 20(3), 32-41.
8. Shadiyeva, G. M., & Urozaliev, E. (2022). HISTORY OF RAILWAY TRANSPORT DEVELOPMENT IN OUR COUNTRY AND FOREIGN EXPERIENCES. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(8), 221-226.
9. Mardiyevna, S. G., & Abdusamatovich, J. J. (2022). SANOAT 4.0 KONSEPSIYASI VA UNGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI RISKLAR. *Current Issues of Bio Economics and Digitalization in the Sustainable Development of Regions*, 712-721.
10. Шакирова, Ф. Б. (2022). ИННОВАЦИОН РИВОЖЛАНИШНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШДА ХОРИЖИЙ ДАВЛАТЛАР ТАЖРИБАСИ. *Journal of new century innovations*, 17(1), 106-113.
11. Шакирова, Ф. Б. (2022). ИННОВАЦИОН РИВОЖЛАНИШ МОДЕЛЛАРИ ВА УЛАРНИНГ ИҚТИСОДИЙ ЎСИШ БИЛАН АЛОҚАДОРЛИГИ. *Journal of new century innovations*, 17(1), 101-105.
12. Шакирова, Ф. Б. (2022). ТРАНСПОРТ СОҲАСИДА ДАВЛАТ-ХУСУСИЙ ШЕРИКЛИК МЕХАНИЗМЛАРИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИНГ ХОРИЖИ ТАЖРИБАСИ. *Journal of new century innovations*, 15(3), 66-74.

- 13.Shakirova, F. B. (2022). INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT MODELS AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH ECONOMIC GROWTH. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(10), 662-665.
- 14.Shakirova, F. B. (2022). ТЕМИР ЙЎЛ ТРАНСПОРТИ СОҲАСИДАГИ ДАВЛАТ-ХУСУСИЙ ШЕРИКЧИЛИК МУНОСАБАТЛАРИ. *Journal of new century innovations*, 16(3), 82-85.
- 15.Shakirova, F. B., & Sattorova, S. B. (2022). “О ‘ЗБЕКИСТОН ТЕМИР YO ‘LLARI” AJ FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XALQARO NAMKORLIK FAOLIYATI. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(9), 4-9.
- 16.Shakirova, F. B. (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ИННОВАЦИОН РИВОЖЛАНИШНИНГ НАЗАРИЯЛАРИ, ШАКЛЛАНИШИ ВА МИЛЛИЙ ИҚТИСОДИЁТ ЎСИШИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШДАГИ ИМКОНИЯТЛАРИ. *Journal of new century innovations*, 16(3), 86-96.
- 17.Шакирова, Ф. Б. (2022). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА НА ОСНОВЕ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(2), 382-390.
- 18.Shadieva, G., & Shakirova, F. (2020). MILLIY INNOVATION TIZIMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INVESTITSIYA VA INNOVATSIYALARNING O‘RNI. *SCIENCE AND INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT*, (4), 9-16.